

ISic0588

I.Sicily inscription 0588

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

breccia

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2018.07.05

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

First noted by Gualtherus in the church of S.Maria 'ad nives' below the Norman Castle, which is perhaps Santa Maria in/di Aracoeli Rediscovered in the late C20 on the roof of the Convento dei Cappuccini

Coordinates

38.070068, 14.703558

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, S. Marco d'Alunzio, Museo della cultura e delle Arti Figurative Bizantine e Normanne

Physical Description

A block of the local pink 'breccia di San Marco' with white veins. Intact top and right, but broken to left, below, and behind.

Dimensions

Height 14 cm

Width 30 cm

Depth 19 cm

Layout

An incomplete single line of Latin letters with a vacat above; the right margin is intact

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: 55 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Liviae·A]ugusti

2. [deae]

3. [municipium]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

[Liviae · Au]gusti, Mommsen, Salinas

Translation (en)

The municipium (dedicates this) to the goddess Livia (wife) of Augustus

Commentary

Salinas in NSA 1880: 194 no.10, followed by Mommsen in CIL 10.7464, assumed that the fragment which they saw reading [- -]GVSTI, in the convent of the Cappuccini was a fragment of the text seen in full by earlier authors starting with Gualtherus and recording a dedication to the deified Livia by the municipium. This fragment was published by Bonanno in 1997/98, after being relocated in the same convent dei Cappuccini (albeit in a different place, on the roof rather than in the steps) in the 1990s. Bonanno did not connect the fragment with the previously recorded text, but given that the fragment is from the upper right of a block and the overlap of location and text it seems a reasonable assumption that this is the surviving fragment of the text first recorded by Gualtherus, notwithstanding the fact that Mommsen and Salinas only read [--]gusti (if the block was, at the time, still embedded in a staircase, it may not have been entirely visible).

Digital identifiers:

TM 491845

EDCS 22100583

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Photo J. Prag